

What do biodiversity genomics researchers need to know about “Digital Sequence Information”?

An information brief and
the ERGA position

What do biodiversity genomics researchers need to know about “Digital Sequence Information”? An information brief and the ERGA position

Authors: Christian de Guttery, Solenne Correard, Ann Mc Cartney, Jennifer A. Leonard, Amber Hartman Scholz, Rebekah Oomen, Camila J. Mazzoni, Robert M. Waterhouse.

Document version: 01.08.2025

1. Purpose and scope.....	2
2. Key resources on CBD COP 16 and the MLM.....	3
3. ERGA Position Statement on CBD COP Decision 16/2 (DSI).....	4
3.1 Commitment to Open Science.....	4
3.2 Recognition of the New Multilateral Mechanism.....	5
3.3 Concerns Requiring Ongoing Attention.....	6
3.4 Pathways to Progress.....	7
3.5 Conclusion.....	7
4. Contact and Further Engagement.....	8

The **European Reference Genome Atlas** (ERGA¹) is a pan-European initiative that aims to facilitate the generation of high-quality reference genomes for the continent’s biodiversity as part of the global Earth BioGenome Project. Serving as the European node of this worldwide endeavour, ERGA brings together researchers and stakeholders to coordinate standardised sampling, sequencing, data management, assembly, and annotation for reference genomes across diverse groups of eukaryotes.

¹ <https://www.erga-biodiversity.eu/>

1. Purpose and scope

This document serves a dual function:

1. **Information brief** to help readers understand new developments on the topic of Digital Sequence Information (DSI) and direct them to appropriate resources that explain CBD COP Decision 16/2² and the new multilateral mechanism (MLM) for DSI.
2. **ERGA position statement** that sets out the ERGA perspective on how CBD COP Decision 16/2 affects open science, equity, and biodiversity genomics.

² The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Conference of the Parties (COP)
<https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-16/cop-16-dec-02-en.pdf>

2. Key resources on CBD COP 16 and the MLM

- ★ Muñoz-García M; DSI Scientific Network; Scholz AH. [Navigating COP16's digital sequence information outcomes: What researchers need to do in practice](#). *Patterns* (N Y). 2025 Mar 14;6(3):101208. doi: 10.1016/j.patter.2025.101208. PMID: 40182173; PMCID: PMC11963070.
- ★ Additional resources on DSI available from the DSI Scientific Network³ website: [Resources – DSI Scientific Network](#)
- ★ To learn more about other topics discussed and decided at COP 16, consult the following overviews from the CBD:
 - [COP 16 in Cali: progress towards making peace with nature | Convention on Biological Diversity](#)
 - [COP 16 has fulfilled its promise to the world | Convention on Biological Diversity](#)
- ★ The Cali Fund:
 - Orozco, P., Scholz, A.H. The Cali Fund promises conservation benefits, but only if countries and businesses take action. *Nat. Rev. Biodivers.* **1**, 276–278 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44358-025-00050-z>.
 - Mathieu Rouard, Amber Hartman Scholz, Michael Halewood, Genetic databases in the era of 'DSI' benefit-sharing, *Trends in Genetics*, Volume 41, Issue 6, 2025, Pages 451-455, ISSN 0168-9525, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2025.03.004>

³ Authors SC, AM-C, AHS, and CM of this position statement are members of the DSI Scientific Network

3. ERGA Position Statement on CBD COP Decision 16/2 (DSI)

3.1 Commitment to Open Science

As a community of researchers and stakeholders dedicated to generating and using genomic data for biodiversity conservation, the European Reference Genome Atlas (ERGA) reaffirms its commitment to open science, in line with the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science adopted by 193 Member States in November 2021⁴. We believe that the free, rapid, and globally accessible exchange of biological data, including digital sequence information (DSI), is essential for advancing biodiversity genomics research and applying its findings to pressing environmental challenges and conservation, as well as global health and food security. Any measures that limit or impede open access, such as charging fees, adding bureaucratic layers, or introducing waiting periods, risk undermining scientists' collective ability to discover, innovate, collaborate, and support evidence-based actions towards conservation measures and biodiversity change monitoring. Nonetheless, we recognize the sovereign rights of each Nation State and Indigenous Peoples over their genetic resources codified in the Convention on Biological Diversity and the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). Additionally, through the Nagoya Protocol, we recognise the rights and interests of Indigenous Peoples and local communities to free, prior and informed consent, data governance and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits for genetic resources, associated traditional knowledge, and related digital sequence information, per national law. We further acknowledge existing capacity gaps, especially where financial resources are limited. To this end, we commit to supporting inclusive and open DSI practices through access to infrastructure, training, and data stewardship, and to promoting fair and equitable benefit-sharing.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMH8546>

3.2 Recognition of the New Multilateral Mechanism

ERGA commends the operationalisation of the multilateral mechanism for sharing benefits arising from DSI at the 16th Conference of the Parties (CBD COP16). This structure, complete with a new global fund, the Cali Fund⁵, governance instruments, and benefit-sharing guidelines, marks a meaningful step towards achieving equity in biodiversity research by supporting benefit-sharing among participating parties. Significantly, the decision enables academic researchers in all countries to continue their work with open and cost-free access to DSI, upholding open science and enabling scientists to advance biodiversity studies without undue financial or administrative barriers.

⁵ https://www.biofin.org/sites/default/files/content/knowledge_products/Cali%20Fund%20Guide%20Final.pdf

3.3 Concerns Requiring Ongoing Attention

While ERGA celebrates these advancements, some concerns warrant close attention:

- i. While ERGA welcomes Decision 16/2, it remains concerned that the decision does not adequately address the critical DSI capacity gap experienced by countries with limited financial resources and regions rich in biodiversity. Such countries, along with Indigenous Peoples (IPs) and Local Communities (LCs), depend strongly on open-access data to enhance research capabilities and conservation efforts. Therefore, ERGA advocates for clearer, more concrete commitments regarding targeted investments, including workshops, direct funding, and technical assistance, to be explicitly integrated into future COP decisions, clarifying how mechanisms like the Cali Fund will support DSI-related capacity-building.
- ii. ERGA supports maintaining transparency, ease of use, and responsible governance in data repositories, which is necessary for sustaining open science. Any increase in administrative demands or data governance complexities, particularly around DSI databases, should not limit researchers' ability to access or use DSI.
- iii. ERGA appreciates the built-in reviews and opportunities to adjust contribution rates, allocation methods, and other elements of the new mechanism. Nonetheless, continuous dialogue with academic institutions, IPs, LCs, commercial stakeholders, and civil society remains indispensable. Policies must adapt to evolving scientific, technological, and geopolitical contexts, ensuring that biodiversity genomics benefits are broadly shared.

3.4 Pathways to Progress

Public DSI archives, in particular the INSDC databases (GenBank, ENA, DDBJ), support biodiversity genomics research. For example, GenBank's March 2025 release⁶ contained approximately 5.56 billion sequence records (~41.96 trillion bases), reflecting rapid growth and genomic data availability. As EMBL-EBI highlights⁷ Open access enables researchers worldwide to easily explore genomic information across numerous species, supporting global initiatives such as Africa Biogenome Project (AfricaBP), ERGA, and the Earth BioGenome Project.

On this shared knowledge foundation, ERGA is piloting the adoption of Local Contexts⁸ Traditional Knowledge and Biocultural Labels, enabling Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities to append culturally appropriate guidance directly to sequence metadata (see the Guidance Documentation for Implementing Labels in ERGA⁹). These Labels travel with the data: they keep the traditional knowledge visible and uphold Indigenous data sovereignty. In short, judicious revisions to existing metadata can preserve the speed and openness that fuel discovery while delivering equity and respect for future demands.

3.5 Conclusion

ERGA lauds the decision's unwavering support for open access to DSI and the more unified, predictable framework that a multilateral mechanism delivers. These proactive measures will help maintain research momentum, a key factor in tackling global biodiversity challenges. Moving forward, attention must be paid to potential unintended barriers, equitable inclusion, and the preservation of open, collaborative research. This framework is expected to facilitate ethical, effective, and equitable genomic investigations that will benefit the entire global community through thoughtful refinement and inclusive engagement.

⁶ <https://ncbiinsights.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2025/03/11/genbank-release-265/>

⁷ <https://www.embl.org/news/science/biodiversity-genomic-data-2022/>

⁸ <https://localcontexts.org/>

⁹ <https://localcontexts.org/guidance-documentation-for-implementing-the-traditional-knowledge-and-biocultural-labels-in-the-european-reference-genome-atlas/>

4. Contact and Further Engagement

Under the new benefit-sharing mechanism, users of DSI are expected to contribute non-monetary benefits (NMB). To assist the scientific community in this endeavor, the ERGA ELSI committee will release supportive resources.

Questions about this statement or ERGA's activities can be directed to the ERGA ELSI Committee via elsi@erga-biodiversity.eu.